

High volumetric capacity non-precious catalyst-based solid state hydrogen storage: Investigations on Magnesium-Nickel alloy nano particles embedded, Nitrogen-rich graphite (Mg₂Ni/N-Gr)

Asalatha Nair*, Sangeetha V., Abinaya S. and Ramaprabhu Sundara

Alternative Energy and Nanotechnology Laboratory (AENL), Nano Functional Materials Technology Centre (NFMTC), Department of Physics, Indian Institute of Technology Madras Chennai 600036, India. E-mail: nair.asalatha@gmail.com

Abstract:

We have analysed the possibilities of low surface area carbon materials as potential hydrogen storage candidates with high capacities- both volumetric and gravimetric; with the help of catalyst-aided reactions; but the noble metal-based catalysts are still a challenge for the bulk amount of industrial production. In this context, catalysts based on non-precious metals are successfully tested. This discussion presents a brief overview of the study on magnesium-nickel alloy nanoparticles embedded in nitrogen-rich graphite (Mg₂Ni/N-Gr).

Keywords: solid state hydrogen storage, magnesium nickel alloy nano particles, spillover mechanism, catalyst nanoparticles, volumetric capacity, graphite.

1. Introduction:

Graphite is a polymorph of carbon formed by the stacking of 2D graphene sheets of carbon hexagons. The stacking of hexagonal basal planes (a x b) along the c-axis leads to the formation of 2D sheets that transform into 3D graphite. The crystallographic unit cell is hexagonal, as shown in Figure 1.12. The theoretical density of graphite is 2.25 g/cm³, while it can be reduced by 1.85 g/cm³ by methods such as mechanical milling. Graphite is a good conductor and has several excellent properties. Here, we aim to explore hydrogen storage in graphite via reactions catalysed by a metal alloy nano catalyst.

Hydrogen storage in magnesium hydride:

Even though MgH₂ is reported as an ideal candidate for reversible hydrogen storage, its thermodynamic instability is pulling it out of the mainstream, as it results in a relatively high hydrogen desorption temperature and slow adsorption/desorption kinetics. The kinetics can be improved dramatically by doping magnesium with transition metals, ball milling, or surface

modification (i.e., reducing the grain size). The typical unfavourable thermodynamic parameters which contribute to the high hydrogen release temperature (above 300 °C) are $\Delta H = 74.4$ kJ/mol and $\Delta S = 135.1$ J/molK, which originates from the enormous lattice energy $[Mg^{2+}H_2^{-1}]_a$ $\Delta H = 2178$ kJ/mol, relative to the bulk Mg ($\Delta H = 147$ kJ/mol)¹⁻⁷. Theoretically, reducing the particle size of Mg can substantially affect its thermodynamic parameters, making it a favourable candidate for the hydrogen storage industry. These insights lead to the synthesis of Mg nanoparticles.

Mg₂Ni/N-Gr:

Doping of Mg with transition metals can make it a reasonable medium for the hydrogen storage industry. Among the various transition metals with high hydrogen affinity, Ni is the most suitable here, as it is less costly than Pd and well complements Mg to enhance its properties. Among all Mg-based alloys, the intermetallic alloy Mg₂Ni is the most recommended for hydrogen storage because of its high stability at ambient conditions and high hydrogen uptake capacity, with fast adsorption/desorption kinetics.

Again, we have already investigated the properties of nitrogen-rich graphite as a high volumetric capacity hydrogen storage material⁸. Hence, we have chosen the nitrogen-rich graphite as the catalyst support matrix for the Mg₂Ni nanoparticles.

2. Experimental section:

Synthesis procedure of Mg₂Ni- N- Gr and Mg₂Ni- B- Gr

The procedure involved here is the same as discussed elsewhere^{8,9}. The as purchased graphite powders were mixed with melamine in (1:1) ratio using sufficient amount of DI water by a mechanical stirring of 15 minutes; following which the required amount of metal precursors (1 wt% standard solutions of MgCl₂ and NiCl₂ · 6H₂O to satisfy the 20 wt% of the targeted loading of Mg and Ni in 2:1 ratio) were added and continued the stirring for 6 hours and finally the mixture was dried overnight in a vacuum oven at 60°C.

The dried mixture is well ground and uniformly loaded into a quartz boat placed in the centre of a tubular furnace, flushed with Argon gas for 10 minutes, and then the heat treatment is started. As the sample temperature reaches 250 °C, hydrogen gas is introduced into the system for 30 minutes. Then the system temperature is raised to 700 °C and held for 30 more minutes.

The furnace was then cooled down to room temperature, and the product was carefully taken out and labelled as Mg₂Ni- N- Gr.

For the synthesis of Mg₂Ni- B- Gr, the above procedure is repeated by replacing the required amount of boric acid with melamine.

Characterizations:

As discussed elsewhere,^{8,9} through an easy and appropriate single-step synthesis process, the ‘as purchased’ graphite sheets were transformed into nitrogen-rich, alloy-catalyst nanoparticle-embedded (Mg₂Ni/N-Gr) hydrogen storage media. The ‘as purchased’ graphite powder consists of two-dimensional sliding sheets. The present synthesis procedure is designed to favour two processes: the decomposition of melamine into nitrogen groups, followed by their subsequent doping within the layers of graphite, and the reduction of Mg and Ni from their corresponding precursors, with their further nucleation as alloy nanoparticles on the nitrogen-rich graphite substrate. When the well-mixed graphite powder with precursors was exposed to a systematic heating procedure in a tubular furnace in the presence of hydrogen and argon, the desired composition of nitrogen, magnesium and nickel was assimilated in the graphite matrix. As the temperature exceeded 280 °C, the melamine started decomposing into nitrogen functional groups, which could subsequently be accommodated in the SP₂ networks of the graphite sheets. Following this, hydrogen gas was introduced into the system, and Mg and Ni were released from their corresponding precursors. Again, when the temperature was raised to 700 °C, Mg and Ni were deposited on the nitrogen-rich sites of the graphite layers as nanoparticle clusters. Thus, the nitrogen sites will favour the nucleation of catalyst nanoparticles. This method successfully immobilises magnesium-nickel alloy catalyst nanoparticles in a 2:1 ratio on a nitrogen-rich graphite substrate. Here, we have adopted the optimised catalyst loading of 20 wt%. Each graphite grain can permit decoration of the nanoparticles on the top and bottom layers, as well as on the edges of the middle layers.

Fig. 1. (A) Normalized XRD patterns of a) $\text{Mg}_2\text{Ni}/\text{N-Gr}$ and b) graphite and (B) Energy Dispersive X-ray analysis of $\text{Mg}_2\text{Ni}/\text{N-Gr}$

Fig. 2. TEM (a) and SEM (b) images of as purchased Graphite

The normalised powder XRD patterns of graphite and $\text{Mg}_2\text{Ni}/\text{N-Gr}$ are shown in Fig. 1. (A). The graphite hexagonal planes are revealed through (002) and (004) peaks. In the $\text{Mg}_2\text{Ni}/\text{N-Gr}$ specimen, since the catalyst has a single face-centred disordered structure (a solid solution), indicating perfect alloying of Ni in the Mg lattice, the peaks are confirmed as the patterns from the alloy planes. These results clearly demonstrate the successful immobilisation of magnesium-nickel alloy nanoparticles on the graphite substrate. Above all, the nitrogen-rich graphite substrate is sufficient to accommodate the catalyst nano-phase in its binary alloy form

without any structural modification, which is an appreciable sign of the projected catalytic activity towards hydrogen as estimated.

Again, the elemental composition and distribution of the samples were analysed using elemental mapping and energy-dispersive X-ray analysis. The EDX spectra (see Fig. 1 (B)) show the composition of elements in the Mg_2Ni - N- Gr sample.

Fig. 3. SEM (a) and (b) and TEM (c) and (d) images of $Mg_2Ni/N-Gr$

The surface morphology of the sample is explored through the microscopic images shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The TEM and SEM images of graphite layers in the as-purchased powdered sample are shown in Fig. 2 (a and b), respectively. When treated via the catalytic chemical vapour deposition synthesis procedure, as explained previously, the pristine graphite layers

became enriched with nitrogen and embedded with catalyst nanoparticles. The SEM and TEM images in Fig. 3 show a random distribution of nanoparticles within the layers. From Fig. 3 (c and d), the size of the embedded nanoparticles is estimated to be ~ 8 nm, which is in agreement with the XRD calculations. In Fig. 3 (d), the marked portion (marked in red colour arrow) shows the single alloy nanoparticle attached to the edge of the graphite sheet. To confirm the spatial distribution of elements in the sample, elemental mapping of the images is performed. The representative elemental mapping of the sample is shown in Fig. 4. It is quite evident from the figure that Mg and Ni alloy nanoparticles are distributed randomly over the nitrogen-rich graphite layers.

Fig. 4. The representative elemental mapping of the Mg₂Ni/N- Gr sample.

The gas adsorbing properties of the present sample were analyzed through the BET surface area and porosity measurements. The data are recorded using the nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77K, as shown in Fig. 5.(A). The observed BET surface area of the Pd₃Co- N- Gr sample is 1.470 m²/g; while for pure graphite it is 1.2021 m²/g. The BJH pore size distribution is also exhibited in Fig. 5. (B).

The isotherms are observed to be of type IV with a hysteresis in the range of (0.45 -0.99) P/P₀; according to Brunauer-Deming-Deming-Teller classification, which is the characteristic of a

meso- porous material. The pore size distribution shows a range of pores between (2-80) nm with a maximum volume at (2- 50) nm, which is meso-porous. These qualities confer perfect gas adsorption properties on the present material. It is observed that the specific surface area of graphite is increased after the decoration of the catalyst nanoparticle. This can be attributed to the uniform distribution of nano-sized alloy catalyst particles, which, in turn, improves the system's catalytic activity as expected. However, some sites, including the catalyst centres, will not be accessible for nitrogen adsorption; they may be active for hydrogen adsorption. Therefore, in practice, the surface area for hydrogen adsorption will be even higher.

Fig. 5. (A) - BET surface area analysis of samples – graphite and Mg₂Ni/N- Gr -The nitrogen adsorption- desorption isotherms and (B) Porosity analysis of graphite and Mg₂Ni/N- Gr samples

3. Hydrogen adsorption studies:

As mentioned elsewhere, the hydrogen adsorption -desorption studies were performed in a Sieverts apparatus (see figure 6) using the pressure reduction method by applying the Van der Waals corrections for the hydrogen gas. The pressure - composition (P-C) isotherms of Mg₂Ni-N- Gr were plotted for different temperatures as shown in Fig. 7. The isotherms were recorded in a temperature range of 25 – 100 °C with a pressure range of (0.1 – 3) MPa. As the sample temperature increases, the storage capacity also increases, as expected, since gas molecules gain enough kinetic energy to overcome the barrier potential.

Figure 6- the schematics of the Sieverts' apparatus used for hydrogen adsorption/desorption studies.

Fig. 7. Hydrogen pressure – composition isotherms of Mg₂Ni/N- Gr

The desorption studies at room temperature show the high reversibility of the adsorption process. From the isotherm study of Mg₂Ni- N- Gr sample, at 2 MPa pressure and room temperature, the storage capacity is estimated as 4.1 ± 0.1 wt% hydrogen. Compared to high-

surface-area carbon materials like graphene, activated carbon, MOFs, or chemically modified carbon materials, this capacity is quite high. For pure graphite or few-layer graphene, the reported value is less than 1 wt % under the same conditions. For the Pd₃Co-N- Gr sample at 2 MPa and room temperature, the capacity is 5.1 ± 0.1 wt%, but here the catalyst cost is several times lower. A maximum storage capacity of 5.6 ± 0.1 wt% at 3 MPa pressure is observed, which supports Mg₂Ni-N-Gr as a potential gravimetric capacity material.

4. Conclusion:

Through a simple one-step synthesis process, a potential high-volumetric and gravimetric-capacity hydrogen storage material with a non-precious catalyst is developed. The synthesis process is scalable and cost-effective, as it modifies the raw material, graphite, in a single step and uses less expensive catalysts. The alloy catalyst mechanism and role of nitrogen in the hydrogen storage capacity of graphite are explored. The present material Mg₂Ni- N- Gr could achieve a maximum gravimetric storage capacity of 5.6 ± 0.1 wt%. Following a similar procedure, we have also examined the hydrogen adsorption/desorption properties of palladium-cobalt alloy particles embedded in boron-rich graphite (Mg₂Ni- B- Gr). Mg₂Ni- B- Gr is found to have a gravimetric capacity of 3.8 ± 0.1 wt% at 25°C temperature and 3MPa hydrogen pressure. The non-precious alloy catalyst nanoparticle, Mg₂Ni, decorated on nitrogen-rich graphite, can considerably reduce production costs. Compared with graphene and other high-surface-area materials-based studies, the present investigations could approach the ideal hydrogen storage material. Through a cost-effective, one-step synthesis process, catalyst nanoparticles are deposited on the carbon supports to exploit synergistic interaction effects. The choice of suitable alloy catalyst nanoparticles could improve GD and VD, enhance the material's kinetics and cycle life, and reduce production costs and hydrogen corrosion effects. All the materials used in the present study are readily available, environmentally friendly, and non-toxic.

5. Supporting Information:

Electronic supplementary information (ESI[†]) includes EDX spectra, hydrogen sorption kinetics, a stability curve, and a table comparing the different materials.

6. Declarations:

Acknowledgement:

Authors declare no competing financial interest. We are thankful to IIT Madras, India, for their support.

Preprint statement:

This is a preprint version (v1, February 2026) of work extracted from the corresponding author's PhD thesis at IIT Madras. This manuscript was previously submitted to *Advanced Materials* and the *Journal of Physical Chemistry* (rejected), and may be submitted to peer-reviewed journals in the future. Uploaded by the corresponding author for open dissemination and timestamping.

Data Availability and Statement:

This manuscript contains experimental results, simulations and theoretical analyses developed as a part of the PhD thesis at IIT Madras. No confidential or proprietary data is disclosed. Full methodology and context are documented in the publicly available IIT Madras PhD thesis repository. Supporting data is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest:

The authors declare no conflicts of interest. This work represents independent PhD research contributions developed under supervision at IIT Madras and is archived by the lead and corresponding author.

Author contributions:

Asalatha Nair*: Conceptualisation, methodology, data acquisition, formal analysis, investigation, original draft preparation, visualisation, project administration, corresponding author.

Sangeetha V: data acquisition help

Abhinaya S: data acquisition help

Sundara Ramaprabu: Supervision and validation.

7. Reference:

1. Harder, S., Spielmann, J., Intemann, J. & Bandmann, H. Hydrogen storage in magnesium hydride: The molecular approach. *Angew. Chemie - Int. Ed.* **50**, 4156–4160 (2011).
2. Vijay Babu, A. R. *et al.* Magnesium hydrides for hydrogen storage: A mini review. *Int. J. ChemTech Res.* **6**, 3451–3455 (2014).
3. Li, Q. *et al.* Characteristics of hydrogen storage alloy Mg₂Ni produced by hydriding combustion synthesis. *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* **20**, 209–212 (2004).
4. Li, Y. *et al.* Thermal Stability of the Mg₂Ni-Based Hydrogen Storage Alloy Doped Ti Element. *Int. J. Heat Technol.* **34**, 245–250 (2016).
5. Li, Q. *et al.* Characteristics of hydrogen storage alloy Mg₂Ni produced by hydriding combustion synthesis. *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* **20**, 209–212 (2004).
6. Leiva, D. R. *et al.* Magnesium-Nickel alloy for hydrogen storage produced by melt spinning followed by cold rolling. *Mater. Res.* **15**, 813–817 (2012).
7. Hanada, N., Ichikawa, T. & Fujii, H. Catalytic Effect of Nanoparticle 3d-Transition Metals on Hydrogen Storage Properties in Magnesium Hydride MgH₂ Prepared by Mechanical Milling. 7188–7194 (2005).
8. Nair, A., V, S., S, A., & Sundara, R. Investigation of palladium- cobalt alloy nanoparticles embedded in nitrogen-rich graphite composite as a high volumetric capacity compact hydrogen storage material. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18678005>
9. Nair, A., & Sundara, R. CONTACT METAL PERMEATION EFFECTS AND POTENTIAL HYDROGEN STORAGE IN CARBON-BASED MATERIALS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18678752>